

The Impact of gender equality on Linguistic Variability Based on Saudi Vision 2030

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The study examined whether Saudi Vision 2030 contributes to gender equality regarding linguistic variety by identifying conversational interruptions, voices and intonations, word choices, and control of a discussion between men and women. The researcher surveyed 63 men and women, gathering quantitative and qualitative data. The findings showed that males do not interrupt women, and women do not interrupt men, and there is no link between interruption and male dominance. Saudi Vision 2030 has fostered gender equality, making it challenging to identify interruptions between men and women and discern any elevated pitches in women. In addition, women were more precise in expressing colors and using emotional language, while men used masculine vocabulary to demonstrate strength. The study found that women were more likely to begin conversations and discuss intimate matters, whereas men preferred to discuss general issues rather than personal ones. The research revealed that Saudi Vision 2030 improved gender equality, resulting in equal influence over conversations between men and women.

Key words: Gender Equality, Phonological Forms, Intonation, Linguistic Variety, Emotion, Saudi Vision 2030

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Introduction

Psycholinguistics researchers and linguists are interested in the idea that men and women speak differently. Researchers investigated how men and women communicate differently, such as pronouncing words, interrupting, pausing, using vocabulary, and asking questions. Many psychologists, sociologists, anthropologists, and other language and gender researchers have been more interested in the differences between men and women than in the similarities. "Gender" doesn't just mean biological sex; it also means how people work and interact with each other (Paltridge, 2012). Cameron (2005) defines gender as "not something a person has, but something that a person does" (p. 49). One of the most crucial aspects of interpersonal understanding is gender awareness.

Mixed-gender interactions are more likely to contain misconceptions than single-gender ones. Activating different parts of the male and female brains for similar language activities explains gender differences in conversational speech. (Singh 2001). This has the potential to improve understanding of language-disordered issues. In many male and female discussions, confusion or misunderstanding occurs because men and women use different conversational conventions and infer meaning. This could be because men and women use different linguistic communication patterns, such as opening and closing conversations. According to Tannen (1990), resolving disparities in conversational styles might help resolve genuine conflicts of interest and discover a common language.

The research aims to determine if gender equality has been the same or different throughout the recent decade compared to the preceding decade. Moreover, it seeks to know whether or not gender equality has assisted women in obtaining their rights. Therefore, the study investigates the influence of gender equality on linguistic variability based on Saudi Vision 2030.

The following are the study's research questions:

1. Does Saudi Vision 2030 contribute to gender equality by detecting conversational interruptions between men and women?
2. Does Saudi Vision 2030 impact gender equality regarding male and female voices and intonations?
3. Does the democratic transition based on Saudi Vision 2030 influence men's and women's vocabulary choices?
4. Does the democratic transition based on Saudi Vision 2030 influence control of a conversation between men and women?

1. Theoretical Framework

A review of literature delved philosophically into two key parts of sociolinguists' arguments and discussions about the distinctions between men and women: Phonological forms (Trudgill, 1972; Weiss, 1970; Lakoff, 1975; Tahta, Wood, & Loewenthal, 1981; Fishman, 1980; Elliot, 1995; Weatherall, 2002), and conversation style is studied in this study, including language selection, questioning, particularly tag questions, the use of interruption, and three methods of directing a conversation (e.g., Jespersen, 1922; Zimmerman & West, 1975; Beattie, 1982; Arise & Johnson, 1983; Coates, 1993; Herring, 1993; Tannen 1993; Bucholtz & Hall, 1995; Bonvillain, 2003; Goddard & Patterson, 2003; Kakava, 2006; Herring & Paolillo, 2006). The term 'sex' is used for biological categories, whereas 'gender' is used for social categories.

1.1. Conversational interruptions

Among the researchers, there are a variety of opinions regarding who interrupts most frequently during conversations, as well as the interpretations given for interrupts. Holmes (1995) defines interruption as a disruptive turn. She claims that several studies substantiate the idea that men disrupt others more than women do. Zimmerman and West (1975) argued that men dominated because they wield more influence in mixed-gender conversations. Therefore, they discovered that males interrupt women more than females interrupt men during such discussions. West (1984) conducted a comparative analysis of the interactions between male and female doctors and their patients. She discovered that male physicians exhibited a higher frequency of interrupting their patients than female doctors. Additionally, male patients demonstrated a greater tendency to interrupt their female doctors compared to when their doctor was male. Wood (1989) demonstrated that male employees frequently interrupt female managers, despite their superior rank.

Many researchers have disputed the idea that men disrupt others more than women do for a variety of reasons. Talbot (1992), for example, argued that Zimmerman and West's (1975) research had a political purpose, and the data they collected was no longer available, leaving them open to criticism. Murray and Covelli's (1988) study gathered data from interviews, meetings with employees, and events, and the findings demonstrated that women can interrupt males in a variety of contexts.

1.2. Voices and intonations

Male and female voices differ from one another in terms of intonation and voice. According to Eakins and Eakins (1978), women have higher-pitched voices than men due to their shorter and thinner vocal cords. Weatherall (2002) provided various explanations for this phenomenon. One of these is the fact that men have larger larynxes, or voice boxes, than women. Thus, "the greater mass and length of vocal cords lead to a slower frequency of vibration of the vocal cords and a lower pitch. Women tend to have higher-pitched voices than men because their vocal cords are shorter and thinner" (Weatherall, 2002, p. 49). He added that "the passage of the vibrating air from the larynx, through a series of resonators (i.e., the mouth, nose, and throat cavities and past the tongue and lips), also influences pitch and other voice qualities" (p. 50).

Culture and social settings can impact voice patterns. The lower-pitched voice is more associated with male behavior (Holmes, 2001). She stated that female politicians strive to use male characteristics, such as a lower-pitched voice because the public likes sounds associated with masculinity. Furthermore, women strive for acceptance in a male-dominated environment. Wardhaugh (2002) reports that someone advised Margaret Thatcher that her voice did not fit her role as the British Prime Minister. They instructed her to lower the tone and range of her voice and speak more slowly. As a result, her voice became a kind of signature. This example shows that men's voices are associated with power and dominance, while women's voices are associated with powerlessness. This power can come from a multitude of sources, including money, knowledge, social status, and gender (Holmes, 1995). She argues that in many communities, women often perceive themselves as inferior or less powerful than men, leading them to use distinct politeness expressions either for their benefit or against others. As a result, this dimension can be beneficial in distinguishing between male and female speech. This dimension is a key component in a variety of politeness theories, including those of Brown and Levinson (1987).

Numerous studies suggest that nervousness, uncertainty, and a lack of strength trigger a woman's inclination to raise her voice. Lakoff (1975) contended that women's use of a higher pitch can sometimes indicate shyness, doubt, and a lack of assertiveness. She stated that in declarative statements, women use a questioning intonation (increasing the pitch of their voice at the end of a statement) to convert them into inquiries, showing hesitation.

1.3. The choice of vocabulary

Numerous researchers have addressed the various approaches to word selection regarding gender inequalities in the vocabulary that men and women choose to use. According to Weatherall (2002), the use of adjectives reflects gender differences. For example, women and children commonly use 'beautiful' and 'emotional' words, whereas men typically employ 'strong' and 'tough' words. Bonvillain (2003) says men use more profanity with other guys than women. For example, men are more likely to use swear words and other derogatory language, whereas women avoid using these words. Hearing profanity causes women to experience feelings of humiliation and embarrassment. A woman strives to use polite and 'lovely' words that indicate empathy, whereas men frequently use unpleasant terms that indicate heartlessness and hardness.

Lakoff (1975) and Deklerk (1992) claimed that women typically employ more specific color terms (such as mauve, beige, and lavender) compared to men. Researchers also found that women usually express their emotions

through "empty adjectives" like "wonderful" or "terrific," whereas men respond generally with specific details like "adorable."

1.4. Control of a conversation

Regarding conversational control, women often initiate new subjects of speech to maintain control over the conversation and focus on personal matters rather than general ones. According to Al-Harashseh (2014), women tend to initiate more topics to sustain the discussion, indicating that women have a greater influence on talks than men. According to Hanafiyeh & Afghari (2014) and Rasekh & Saeb (2015), women not only start subjects but also prefer discussing intimate topics to engage in debate, particularly on private matters. Through the intention of such subjects, women can guide a conversation according to their preferences, thereby exerting dominance over the discourse.

1.5. Saudi Vision 2030

Saudi Crown Prince and Prime Minister Mohammed bin Salman announced Saudi Vision 2030, a government initiative to increase economic diversification and improve the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's public and commercial service sectors, including health, education, infrastructure, recreation, and tourism.

Vision 2030 aims to diversify Saudi Arabia's economy, reduce its dependence on oil, liberalize the private sector, and attract investors and visitors. The Saudi government first announced this on April 25, 2016. Moreover, it aims to strengthen the private sector and create new jobs by investing 1.8 trillion dollars in infrastructure, education, housing, and health care over a decade.

2. Method

2.1. Participants

The selection of not only adequate tools but also an appropriate sample determines the quality of a research study (Cohen et al., 2018). Data collection from the entire population of Qassim province will be difficult due to a multitude of issues, such as accessibility and time constraints. The researcher should choose a limited group of participants representative of the entire population for data collection (Cohen et al., 2018). Cohen et al. (2018) and Bryman (2011) distinguish between two types of sampling: probability, where each participant has an equal chance of receiving a nomination to participate in the study, and non-probability, where certain participants are more likely to participate than others. Wu & Chen (2006) classify various types of non-probability sampling, including purposive, convenience, restriction, quota sampling, and volunteer sampling. The present study will take place in Buriaydh City Hospitals, Saudi Arabia. The employees' average age surveyed was between 30-50 years old.

2.2. Instrument

The primary approach for this study was quantitative (a questionnaire), whereas the secondary method was qualitative (a semi-structured interview). The researcher utilized the Likert scale throughout the questionnaire. The closed-ended options on this scale, such as "strongly agree," "agree," "undecided," "disagree," and "strongly disagree," allow respondents to respond explicitly (Dörnyei, 2007). The researcher prepared 15 items for quantitative surveys (Appendix A).

In contrast, the semi-structured interview questions, as presented in Appendix B, focus on students' experiences after participating in the study. This could provide additional information about how participants perceive the impact of gender equality on linguistic variety under Saudi Vision 2030.

The researcher designed the statements of the questionnaire and interview to achieve validity and reliability. According to Field (2009), validity measures what should be measured, whereas reliability is the ability to conduct it in different contexts and give similar results. The researcher made statements based on previous studies as well as his extensive experience in discourse, gender, teaching, and research. To ensure the study's reliability, the survey can be applied in various scenarios, such as when people of different genders are working together in one location.

2.3. Procedure

After creating a questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale in Google Forms and distributing it via WhatsApp to a minimum of 200 men and women working in Buriyadh's hospitals (e.g., Central Hospital, Maternity, and Children's Hospital) in the Qassim region of Saudi Arabia for the quantitative survey, only 63 of them submitted their responses. Because the study aims to collect data from a place of mixed gender, hospitals were the best place to conduct it. For the structured interviews, the researchers selected four men and women working in the same hospitals to participate in the study. A survey and interview aimed to gather information on gender equality throughout this decade compared to the preceding decade.

2.4. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics determined the frequency and mean score for each question in the questionnaire. At the onset, it was crucial to note that the study's participants were 63, 43 males and 20 females working in hospitals in Qassim Province, as shown in Figure 1. The researcher randomly selected four males and females to conduct the follow-up interview. To gather their thoughts, the researcher asks a few questions (see Appendix B). He used thematic analysis (Boyatzis, 1998) to investigate students' attitudes and perceptions of the impact of gender equality on linguistic variability in light of Saudi Vision 2030.

Figure 1
Gender distribution ($N = 63$)

3. Results

The researcher organized and analysed the data collected on research instruments using five thematic categories, which emerged as responses to each research question formulated for the study.

3.1. Research Question 1: Does Saudi Vision 2030 contribute to gender equality by detecting conversational interruptions between men and women?

Four items (2, 3, 4, and 5) in this theme could be divided into subfactors.

3.1.1. Men interrupt women more than women interrupt men

For statement two, a total of 41% and 22% disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively, that men interrupt women more than women interrupt men, whereas 13% agreed, 8% strongly agreed, and 16% were undecided, as shown in Figure 2. According to these findings, a majority of participants don't believe that men interrupt women more than women interrupt.

Figure 2

Men interrupt women more than women interrupt ($N = 63$)

3.1.2. Interruptions for dominance, taking turns, and directing the discourse

The results of item (3) clearly show that 37% of participants disagreed and 14% strongly disagreed with the statement that male speakers use interruptions to dominate, get their turn, and control the speech, while only 16% and 8% agreed with it and 25% were unsure, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Interruptions for dominance, taking turns, and directing the discourse ($N = 63$)

3.1.3. Interruptions and their association with male dominance or controlling discourse

Item (4) showed that 24% and 3% of respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively, with the statement that there is no connection between interruptions and male dominance or controlling speech. In contrast, 33% and 14% of respondents agreed and strongly agreed with the statement, respectively, while 26% were undecided, as shown in Figure 4. According to the results, almost half of the participants (47%) believed that there was no correlation between interruption and male dominance or control of speech.

Figure 4

Interruptions and their relationship to male dominance (N = 63)

3.1.4. Vision 2030 Saudi Arabia and gender interruptions

According to item (5), a total of 30% and 10% agreed and strongly agreed, respectively, with the statement, 'Because of Vision 2030, it has become difficult to detect any interruptions between men and women'. In contrast, 11% disagreed with the statement, 8% strongly disagreed, and 41% remained undecided, as illustrated in Figure 5. Therefore, it was difficult to identify any interruptions between men and women due to the promotion of gender equality by Saudi Vision 2030.

Figure 5

Vision 2030 and gender interruptions (N = 63)

3.2. Research Question 2: Does Saudi Vision 2030 impact gender equality regarding male and female voices and intonations?

This research question is addressed by four items (6, 7, 8, and 9), which may be broken down into sub-factors:

3.2.1. A higher pitch of voice

Item 6 asks if women's voices are higher pitched than men's when speaking. Most of the target population (40% disagreed and 8% strongly disagreed) believed that women do not talk in a higher pitch than men. This indicates that over half of the participants believe there is no significant difference in voice pitch between men and women. However, 25% agreed, and 8% strongly agreed with the statement, while 19% remained indecisive, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6

Voice pitch of men and women (N = 63)

3.2.2. The relationship between a higher pitch and thinner vocal cords

Item (7) investigates whether women's higher-pitched vocals are due to weaker vocal cords. The results indicated that just 10% agreed, 6% strongly agreed, and 46% were doubtful. In contrast, 30% disagreed, and 8% strongly disagreed, with the assumption that women have higher-pitched voices than men because their vocal cords are shorter and thinner, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7

Higher pitch and thinner of vocal cords (N = 63)

3.2.3. The correlation between a higher pitch and feelings of hesitation, uncertainty, and lack of assertiveness

Item (8) clarifies whether speaking in a louder tone of voice indicates hesitancy, doubt, or a lack of assertiveness. 21% disagreed, 10% strongly disagreed, and 27% were undecided. In comparison, 33 agreed and 9% strongly agreed with the statement that women’s use of a higher pitch can be indicative of hesitancy, uncertainty, and a lack of assertiveness, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8
Higher pitch and hesitancy, uncertainty, and a lack of assertiveness (N = 63)

3.2.4. Saudi Vision 2030 and high pitches and intonations

Item (9) discusses the influence of Saudi Vision 2030 on gender equality, including recognizing any higher pitches and intonations. According to the findings, only 14% agreed, 2% strongly agreed, 25% disagreed, 8% strongly disagreed, and the remaining 51% were unsure, as shown in Figure 9. This means Saudi Vision 2030 has promoted gender equality, making it difficult to detect any higher pitches and intonations for women.

Figure 9
Vision 2030 and detecting high pitches and intonations (N = 63)

3.3. Research Question 3: Does the democratic transition based on Saudi Vision 2030 influence men's and women's vocabulary choices?

The third question, which can be divided into sub-factors, was answered by three items (10, 11, and 12):

3.3.1. Identifying color descriptions

The findings of item 10 revealed that 49% strongly agreed and 35% agreed with the statement that women typically use greater precision in describing color descriptions (e.g., mauve, beige, and lavender) than men. Only 3% and 2% disagreed with the statement, and 11% were uncertain, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10
Colour descriptions (N = 63)

3.3.2. Using emotional and tough words

The results of item 11 showed that 37% agreed and 22% strongly agreed with the statement that women tend to use beautiful and emotional words when talking to each other, while men tend to use strong and tough words to express

their masculinity. However, Figure 11 indicates that 14% disagreed, 10% strongly disagreed, and 17% were undecided.

Figure 11

Emotional and tough words (N = 63)

3.3.3. Saudi Vision 2030 and Polite Discourse

The findings of item 12 revealed that 30% agreed and 21% strongly agreed with the impact of Vision 2030 on avoiding harsh and tough words and talking politely. Only 9% disagreed, 8% strongly disagreed, and 32 were undecided, as illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12

Vision 2030 and using polite and nice words (N = 63)

3.4. Research Question 4: Does the democratic transition based on Saudi Vision 2030 influence control of a conversation between men and women?

This research question was answered in five items (13, 14, 15, 16, and 17) and can be divided into sub-factors as follows:

3.4.1. Starting new conversations to dominate the conversation

Participants' answers to item 13 indicated that 36% agreed, 16% strongly agreed, and 32 were undecided, whereas only 13% disagreed and 3% strongly disagreed, as shown in Figure 13. This finding revealed that the majority believed that women preferred initiating new topics to maintain and dominate the conversation.

Figure 13

Initiating new topics to dominate the conversation ($N = 63$)

3.4.2. Preferring intimate conversations over general discussions for women

The result of item 14 showed that 30% agreed, 10% strongly agreed and 31% undecided, whereas 26% disagreed, and 3% strongly disagreed, as shown in Figure 14. This indicates that 40% of the total participants believed that women prefer to talk about personal topics with others rather than talking about general topics.

Figure 14

Personal rather than general talk ($N = 63$)

3.4.3. Valuing general talk over private ones for men

For item 15, Figure 15 demonstrates that 45% agreed, 29% strongly agreed, 18% were unsure, and 8% disagreed. According to this finding, 69% of respondents agreed with the statement that men would rather discuss general topics with others than personal ones.

Figure 15

General rather than personal talk ($N = 63$)

3.4.4. Men's Disagreements during social interactions

Item 16 indicates that 24% agreed, 10% strongly agreed, and 22% undecided, whereas 38% disagreed and 6% strongly disagreed with the statement that men tend to disagree more than women when interacting and discussing with each other, as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16

Disagreeing men socially (N = 63)

3.4.5. Saudi Vision 2030 and Discourse Control

Regarding item 17, the findings indicate that, as illustrated in Figure 17, 39% agreed, 11% strongly agreed, 32% undecided, 13% disagreed, and 5% severely disagreed. According to this research, half of the participants said that Saudi Vision 2030 impacted gender equality regarding discussion control, with no one having greater influence than the other.

Figure 17

Vision 2030 and conversational control (N = 63)

3.5. Interview Results

The researcher conducted interviews to complement the questionnaire and gather additional insights into the impact of gender equality on linguistic variability, as outlined in Saudi Vision 2030. He randomly selected four individuals, two men and two women (two from the Central Hospital, and others from the Maternity, and Children's Hospital), who work at Buriyadh City to share their perspectives on how Saudi Vision 2030 promotes gender equality across different languages. Table 1 presents the results of the thematic analysis of the semi interview.

Table 1

Themes addressing participants' perceptions towards the impact of Saud Vision 2030 on gender equality and linguistic variability

Themes	Answer
Gender equality throughout this decade compared to the preceding decade.	Respondent (A) thinks that gender equality is visible in various professional settings. Respondent (B) believes that we are moving in the correct direction toward equality. Respondent (C) thought that women's rights have increased, and gender equality has made amazing progress. Respondent (D) thought that men and women have attained equality in terms of rights, employment, and high positions.
Influence of Saudi Vision 2030 on Gender Equality.	Respondent (A) believed that the trend towards gender equality has increased since the implementation of Saudi Vision 2030. Respondent(B) thought that gender equality has assisted women in obtaining their rights. Respondent(C) thought that women's perspectives had gained greater trust, and she actively participated in collaborative activities. Respondent(D) thought that men and women had attained equality; yet, males retained greater authority and domination.

Here is a detailed description of the interview:

Respondent A

Respondent A mentioned that, at present, the impact of gender equality is noticeable in several professional environments. Most meetings or lectures held during working hours have members of both genders, and this trend has increased since the implementation of Saudi Vision 2030. Even though equality is not justice, each has advantages and traits that set it apart. They may share a location but have distinct traits.

Respondent B

Currently, there is no gender equality; however, we are progressing in the right direction towards equality. We should show respect for all genders and refrain from speaking superior to others. Vision 2030 has largely led to the official recognition of women's rights. Both males and females collaborate in collective decision-making.

Respondent C

Respondent C stated clearly that, aligned with Vision 2030, women's rights have increased, and gender equality has made amazing progress. Vision 2030 aims to protect women's rights and acknowledge their inherent capabilities. Hence, her viewpoint has gained more trust, and she actively participates in collaborative efforts. Numerous locations

and occupations employ her, showcasing her exceptional success. Saudi Vision 2030 incorporates strict principles to improve respect for women, and workplaces must treat them fairly.

Respondent D

Respondent D stated that the late King Abdulaziz, the first king of Saudi Arabia, and his sons initiated societal change. Throughout the Kingdom's development since its founding, women's rights have undergone successive protections, culminating in this auspicious era. For instance, King Faisal's reign established the right to education. Even though men and women have achieved equality in rights, jobs, and high positions under Saudi Vision 2030, males have retained more authority and dominance. Females have a greater knowledge of personal and family difficulties.

4. Discussion

The study investigates the impact of gender equality on linguistic variety. In other words, it seeks to determine if gender equality has remained consistent or changed during the last decade compared to the previous decade. Furthermore, it seeks to determine whether Saudi Vision 2030 contributed to gender equality and benefited women in gaining their rights. The researcher obtained valid and trustworthy results using a mixed-methods approach, which included 17 items specially developed for quantitative surveys and 2 items specifically intended for qualitative structured interviews. The study's findings highlighted the responses to the four research questions: (1) Does Saudi Vision 2030 contribute to gender equality by detecting conversational interruptions between men and women? (2) Does Saudi Vision 2030 impact gender equality regarding male and female voices and intonations? (3) Does the democratic transition based on Saudi Vision 2030 influence men's and women's vocabulary choices? (4) Does the democratic transition based on Saudi Vision 2030 influence the control of a conversation between men and women?

The research's findings can be summarised as follows:

4.1. Saudi Vision 2030 contributes to gender equality by detecting conversational interruptions between men and women

According to Figures 2, 3, 4, and 5, the majority of polled participants stated that neither men nor women interrupted each other during conversions. 51% said that men do not interrupt people to dominate, get their turn, and control their speech, while 47% said there was no link between interruptions and male dominance or controlling speech. As a result, 40% believed that Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 promoted gender equality and made it harder to discover or detect any interruptions between men and women. The study's findings contradict previous research, including Zimmerman and West (1975), West (1984), Wood (1989), and Holmes (1995), who claimed that several studies support the notion that men interrupt others more than women, and males interrupt women more than females interrupt men during discussions. This study also contradicts West's (1984) comparative analysis study, which indicated that male physicians interrupted their patients more frequently than female doctors. The results of this study demonstrated that Vision 2023 has a positive impact on gender equality and that men are more conscious than before of taking turns speaking, controlling the conversation, and dominating the discourse.

4.2. Saudi Vision 2030 contributes to gender equality by identifying high pitches between men and women

Figures 6 and 7 indicated that 48% of participants believed that women's voices are not higher pitched than men's, and 38% did not think that women have higher-pitched voices than men because their vocal cords are shorter and thinner than those of men. The participants underscored this result by asserting that Saudi Vision 2030 has fostered gender equality, making it challenging to discern any elevated pitches and intonations in women. The study's findings contradict some previous studies, such as Eakins and Eakins (1978) and Weatherall (2002), which found that women have higher-pitched voices than men because of shorter and thinner vocal cords. On the contrary, the study's result in Figure 8 revealed that 42% of respondents surveyed supported the idea that women's use of a higher pitch can be indicative of hesitancy, uncertainty, and a lack of assertiveness. This result is in line with Lakoff (1975), who claimed that women's higher pitch is a sign of shyness, doubt, and a lack of assertiveness. Moreover, Holmes (2001) emphasized that female politicians tend to use male characteristics, such as lower-pitched voices.

4.3. Saudi Vision 2030 roles in the choice of vocabulary for gender

According to Figure 10, 84% of participants agreed that women were more precise in expressing color (such as mauve, beige, and lavender) than men. This result is in agreement with Lakoff (1975) and Deklerk (1992), who found that women tend to use precise and concise colors such as lavender or mauve compared to men who know more common colors such as black, yellow, and red. Similarly, Figure 11 demonstrated that most respondents believed that women use beautiful and emotive phrases when communicating with one another, whereas males use strong and tough terms to represent their masculinity. This is in line with Weatherall (2002) and Bovillain (2003), who found that women use emotional words, whereas men use profanity and tough words. Women experience embarrassment when they encounter any profanity (Bovillain, 2003). Furthermore, the study's findings found that more than half of the participants demonstrated a beneficial impact of Saudi Vision 2030 on gender equality by avoiding harsh words from men and adopting polite words when conversing with one another.

4.4. Saudi Vision 2030 Effect on the Control of Conversation between men and women

As shown in Figures 13 and 14, the majority of participants believed that women initiate new topics to maintain and dominate the conversation, and they preferred to discuss personal topics with others over general ones. Similarly, the study's result revealed that most participants (74%) thought that men prefer to talk about general topics with others rather than personal topics, as shown in Figure 15. These results align with the findings of Al-Harabsheh's (2014) and Hanafiyeh & Afghari's (2014) studies, which indicate that women initiate more conversations and discuss intimate topics than men. This suggests that women have a greater influence on conversations and exert dominance over the discourse. On the other hand, the study found that men don't prefer to disagree more than women when talking with each other, as shown in Figure 16. The study demonstrated that Saudi Vision 2030 has had a positive impact on gender equality, resulting in equal control over conversations between men and women, as illustrated in Figure 17.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the influence of Saudi Vision 2030 on gender equality and linguistic variability. It examines whether Saudi Vision 2030 contributes to gender equality by detecting any conversational interruptions, higher pitches, choosing precise vocabulary, and controlling a conversation between men and women.

According to the literature analysis and this study on Saudi Vision 2030's impact on gender equality and linguistic variety, the following implications were made:

- There is no correlation between interruption and male dominance or control of speech.
- Men do not interrupt women, and women do not interrupt men.
- In addition to promoting gender equality, Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 made it more difficult to find or detect any interruptions between men and women. Gender fosters mutual understanding and respect among individuals, encouraging them to communicate without interruption or interference.
- Women do not speak at a higher vocal pitch than men. Therefore, there is no statistically significant variation in voice pitch between males and females.
- Women don't typically have higher-pitched voices than men due to their shorter and thinner vocal cords.
- Women's usage of a higher pitch may be a sign of timidity, lack of confidence, and lack of assertiveness.
- Saudi Vision 2030 has fostered gender equality, making it challenging to discern any elevated pitches and intonations in women.
- Women were more exact in expressing colors like mauve, beige, and lavender than men.
- Women use emotional language to communicate, while men use masculine language to demonstrate strength.
- Saudi Vision 2030 promoted gender equality by encouraging men to use polite language and avoid aggressive phrases.
- While males prefer to discuss general issues with others rather than personal ones, women initiate more conversations and discuss intimate topics than men to control the conversation.
- Men don't prefer to disagree more than women when talking with each other.
- Saudi Vision 2030 has had a positive impact on gender equality, resulting in equal control over conversations between men and women.

Suggestions are provided to researchers who plan to perform similar studies in the future to study if gender equality has been the same or different throughout the last decade compared to the previous decade. The study used a questionnaire as the primary instrument and an interview as a supplement, but it could also use discourse analysis to track changes in respondents' speech. Furthermore, the study collected data in hospitals, a setting where men and women collaborated and communicated with each other. Conducting research in various fields, such as banks and telecommuting companies, may yield further results.

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